

The formation of hr-managers' psychological and pedagogical competence in the framework of corporate training: the main concepts and categories of research

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the study of HR-managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation in the framework of corporate training. The purpose of the article is defined as following: to provide the definition of its main concepts and categories. The results of the analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature devoted to the problem under research are highlighted. It was determined that the competence is a basic characteristic that determines the ability and readiness of an individual to solve problems and tasks in daily life, based on the practical use of the knowledge system, as well as life experience. The professional competence is an integral characteristic of a manager which encompasses the system of knowledge, skills for its practical application, personal and professional values and attitudes, which allow him to solve problems in professional environment which is characterised with rapidity of change and uncertainty. The psychological and pedagogical competence of a HR manager is interpreted as an integrative feature, which includes knowledge and skills in the field of psychology and pedagogy, necessary for the organization of continuous development as well as wellbeing of the company's employees, contributes to ensuring the efficiency of professional activity in general and solving complex problems in non-standard situations of the professional environment, as well as inclinations, orientations and strategies for the development of one's own general and professional personal culture, deepening and accumulation of experience in the field of HR management. The term "corporate training" refers to the company's activity, aimed at organizing continuous training of its employees with the aim of mastering or deepening their knowledge, forming, developing, improving professional and key competencies, revealing their talents, which is organized in accordance with the company's development strategy as a learning organization, taking into account the needs and interests of the staff.

Keywords: HR-manager, competence, professional competence, psychological and pedagogical competence, corporate training.

Формування психолого-педагогічної компетентності HR-менеджерів в умовах корпоративного навчання: основні поняття та категорії дослідження

Анотація. Стаття присвячена дослідженню формування психолого-педагогічної компетентності HR-менеджерів в умовах корпоративного навчання. Мета статті – дати

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визначення її основних понять і категорій. Висвітлено результати аналізу науково-педагогічної літератури, присвяченої досліджуваній проблемі. Визначено, що компетентність є базовою характеристикою, яка визначає здатність і готовність особистості вирішувати проблеми та завдання у повсякденному житті на основі практичного використання системи знань, а також життєвого досвіду. Професійна компетентність – це інтегральна характеристика менеджера, яка охоплює систему знань, умінь і навичок для їх практичного застосування, особистих і професійних цінностей та установок, які дозволяють йому вирішувати проблеми у професійному середовищі, що характеризується швидкістю змін і невизначеністю. Психолого-педагогічна компетентність HR-менеджера трактується як інтегративна ознака, яка включає знання та вміння в галузі психології та педагогіки, необхідні для організації неперервного розвитку та благополуччя працівників компанії, сприяє забезпеченню ефективності професійної діяльності в цілому та вирішенню складних завдань у нестандартних ситуаціях професійного середовища, а також нахилів, орієнтацій і стратегій розвитку власної загальної та професійної особистісної культури, поглиблення та накопичення досвіду у сфері управління персоналом. Термін «корпоративне навчання» означає діяльність компанії, спрямовану на організацію неперервного навчання її співробітників з метою оволодіння або поглиблення їхніх знань, формування, розвитку, вдосконалення професійних і ключових компетентностей, розкриття їхніх талантів, яка організовується відповідно зі стратегією розвитку компанії як організації, що навчається, з урахуванням потреб та інтересів персоналу.

Ключові слова: HR-менеджер, компетентність, професійна компетентність, психолого-педагогічна компетентність, корпоративне навчання.

Introduction

At the beginning of the 21st century, special attention is paid to the problem of preservation and further development of human capital. In the conditions of globalization, which affects all spheres of life without exception, the intensive development of information and communication technologies, ensuring openness and access to new knowledge, the introduction of innovations and start-ups into the practice of the economic and business spheres, the level of competition increases. This requires modern companies and enterprises to improve their own activities, to take care of the continuous development of their employees to improve their professional competence, to advance the management system, to form a corporate culture, etc.

The analysis of recent research and publications. The problem of training HR-managers, formation of their professional competence, features of their professional activity is reflected in scientific publications of representatives of various sciences. Researchers Cooke, Schuler, , & Varma analyzed the topics of publications related to HR-management and found out that the following issues are of greatest scientific interest: "Employee creativity and innovation; Talent management and mobility; Performance management; Workplace inequality, employee voice, and diversity management; (New) employment modes and work life balance; Cross-country comparative studies on particular HRM themes; Offshore outsourcing and implications for HRM; Multinational firms from Asia operating across the globe; Multinational firms operating in Asia; The role of leadership styles, culture and employee behaviors; Psychological contracts; Corporate social responsibility, employee well-being and resilience" [12, 2].

The analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature shows that it is worth focusing attention on defining the main concepts and categories of research in order to ensure their correct use in research work.

The formulation of article purpose. The purpose of our article is to analyse the scientific resources and provide the definition of the main concepts and categories of the research

dedicated to the problem of HR-managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation in the framework of corporate training.

Results

Special importance is attached to HR management, as a company activity aimed at ensuring the efficiency of the use of employees to achieve individual and organizational goals, which are correlated with the general strategy of the company's development [16]. HR management is considered from several perspectives: organizational and functional. From an organizational perspective, HR management has a direct connection with all employees of the company and all departments whose functions include work with personnel. In the context of the functional dimension, HR management is considered as activity aimed at the formation of the general strategy of the company's development; the analysis of available personnel and forecasting of the company's needs in the frame of short-term goals and long-term vision; the search for highly qualified specialists, their selection and involvement in the company; the organization of continuous professional development of the company's personnel, which can include both improvement of professional competence and retraining of employees; the implementation of mentoring in career management of company employees; the development of a system of remuneration and stimulation of employees, etc.

The content of the manager's work organization encompasses the scientifically based solutions to such issues as the distribution and cooperation of employees' work in the department or company, the choice of the optimal system and work methods, the selection and placement of personnel, the organization of workplaces and the creation of an effective production environment for company employees. Their specific solution is determined by the applied methods and leadership style of a manager, his general education and professional qualification level, the improvement of which is one of the most important tasks [4].

Taking into account the topicality of the problem of company's employees professional development, the need to ensure the efficiency of their use, we attach great importance to the HR management and their professional competence. In our study, which is devoted to the research of HR managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation in the framework of corporate training, it is worth clarifying the main concepts and categories which are used in the text.

A large and growing body of scientific and pedagogical literature has investigated the competency-based approach and its popularity in educational sphere. This proves that the initial professional training of specialists is carried out on the basis of a competency-based approach, which involves a clear description of educational programs' content, the definition of expected learning outcomes, as well as knowledge, abilities and skills, professional and personal values and attitudes, which are integrative components of a specialist's professional competence [8].

In our study, the definition of such concepts and categories as competence and professional competence is provided. We started the definition of the term "competence" with Merriam Webster Dictionary [18]. In this dictionary it is determined that "competence is the quality or state of being competent: such as the quality or state of having sufficient knowledge, judgment, skill, or strength (as for a particular duty or in a particular respect); legal authority, ability, or admissibility; the ability to function or develop in a particular ways; the ability of embryonic cells and tissue to undergo differentiation in response"; as well as "a sufficiency of means for the necessities and conveniences of life" [18].

In Collins Dictionary one can find the definition of the concept "competence" as following: "the state of being legally competent or qualified", as well as "ability, skill, talent, capacity, expertise, proficiency, capability" [11]. Competence is determined as "the ability to do something in a satisfactory or effective way" [17]. Škrinjarić claims that "competences are

strongly associated with mastering complex situations (contradictory information, informal collaboration, and abstract, dynamic, and highly integrated processes) demanded by modern-day employers and transcend the level of skills and/or abilities, given their synergistic and inter-related nature” [24, 4]. The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development provides the definition of competences as “more than just knowledge and skills. It involves the ability to meet complex demands, by drawing on and mobilizing psychosocial resources (including skills and attitudes) in a particular context” [21, 4].

This study interprets competence as a basic characteristic that determines the ability and readiness of an individual to solve problems and tasks in daily life, based on the practical use of the knowledge system, as well as life experience. The confirmation of the correctness of author’s interpretation can be found in the scientific and pedagogical literature, which highlights various aspects of the research problem, in particular, the formation of professional competence of specialists in various branches of the economy [13].

Recently, considerable evidence has accumulated to show that competence should be interpreted as personality quality. “Professional competence of a modern specialist involves: knowledge of theoretical foundations, means and methods of performing professional tasks; the ability to analyze, forecast one's activities and independently choose means and methods of action in certain specific situations; ability for self-development and self-realization of mastery modern scientific achievements and their implementation; positive attitude towards the future professional activity” [7, 206].

We distinguish the components of competence among which there are knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. In various dictionaries the notion “knowledge” is determined as “understanding of or information about a subject that you get by experience or study, either known by one person or by people generally”; “awareness, understanding, or information that has been obtained by experience or study, and that is either in a person’s mind or possessed by people generally” [9]; “acquaintance with facts, truth, or principles, as from study or investigation; general erudition; familiarity or conversance, as with a particular subject or branch of learning” [17]; “the facts or experiences known by a person or group of people” [11]. In the context of our research we conceptualise the category “knowledge” as an integral component of the competence, which refers to theoretical and applied comprehension of subject, its essence and features.

In Merriam Webster dictionary one can find the definition of the notion “skills” as “the ability to use one’s knowledge effectively and readily in execution or performance”, “dexterity or coordination especially in the execution of learned physical tasks” “a learned power of doing something competently: a developed aptitude or ability” [18]. McMillan Dictionary defines the concept “skills” as following: “the ability to do something well, usually as a result of experience and training” [17]. Škrinjarić provides the definition of the term “skills” as “automated components of tasks, which are undertaken with a relatively low mind control and include routine jobs” [24, 4].

“Value” is interpreted in dictionaries as follows: “the importance or worth of something for someone”, “the beliefs people have, especially about what is right and wrong and what is most important in life, that control their behaviour” [9]; “something (such as a principle or quality) intrinsically valuable or desirable” [18]; “the moral principles and beliefs of a person or group” [11].

The category “attitude” is defined as “a feeling or opinion about something or someone, or a way of behaving that is caused by this” [9]; “a mental position with regard to a fact or state”; “a feeling or emotion toward a fact or state” [18]; “the way a person thinks and behaves”; “a distinctive quality, appearance, or manner”; “a way of dealing with a matter” [11].

In our research we consider categories “values” and “attitudes” through the prism of personal and professional features and define them as the integral components of a

competence, which reflect a valuable personal standard, a socio-psychological construct of a person, determines the direction and content of his behavior and activity, reflects his personal position, attitude to the world, to himself, and results in building relationships with others.

In McMillan Dictionary, “ability is the level of skill that someone has in a particular job or activity” [17]. Merriam Webster Dictionary determines “ability as the quality or state of being able (physical, mental, or legal power) to do something; competence in doing something; natural aptitude or acquired proficiency” [18].

Kolisnyk’s study found that the requirements for management are currently relevant: “... professional competence; formation of personal and professional responsibility based on economic thinking, universal human values and morality; readiness to analyse and evaluate problems, tasks, situations, readiness to make decisions; communicative competence – knowledge of at least one foreign language, mastery of oral and written literary, ability to prepare documents that are necessarily included in the field of professional activity, computer literacy, mastery of modern means of communication; readiness and desire for conscious, permanent, personal and professional improvement, as well as professional development” [4]. Scientists consider the need for the formation of other components of professional competence, in particular, emotional intelligence. Zagray interprets emotional intelligence as “a construct that consists of five main elements, such as: self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation, and social skills” [1, 47].

The clear definition and characteristic of competences justifies the use of certain criteria, with the help of which they can be identified and evaluated. Among them we distinguish the name of the competence as the ability to perform a certain professional action; the descriptors which are considered as characteristic of learning outcomes, special features of specialist’s readiness to demonstrate relevant competences; the behavioural indicators (standards of behaviour) as descriptions of the most effective ways, methods, techniques, technologies of performing professional actions and expected results; the degree of competence importance for the position HR manager; the diagram of the competence development level of an applicant for the position of HR manager [3].

Considering the results of recent research, professional competence can broadly be defined as an integral characteristic of a manager which encompasses the system of knowledge, skills for its practical application, personal and professional values and attitudes, which allow him to solve problems in professional environment which is characterised with rapidity of change and uncertainty.

It is worth emphasizing that the problem of competence formation as well as HR management is reflected not only in the scientific works of theorists, but also in documents of the international [15; 25], state level [6; 19], professional associations and organizations [10; 23], companies and enterprises, which reflect the requirements of the labour market and employers, the demands of society, and the interests of various stakeholders.

Since HR managers work with people, the problem of their psychological and pedagogical competence formation, which we consider as a component of the professional competence of an HR manager, is obvious. Psychological and pedagogical competence as a component of the professional competence of a modern specialist is studied from the perspective of various professions.

Analysing the psychological and pedagogical competence of civil security specialists, Ivashchenko concludes: “the content of psychological and pedagogical competence involves: psychological and pedagogical knowledge; psychological and pedagogical skills (organizational, communicative, gnostic); motivation to master psychological and pedagogical competence, aspiration to acquire a high level of professional competence; psychological maturity (ability to take responsibility for one’s own actions, life and professional self-realization); the ability to quickly and creatively master professional knowledge and skills and

implement them in practical activities; the ability to constructive cooperation and partnership relations with people with simultaneous assurance of personal independence and self-respect; the desire for education, self-improvement and creativity” [2, 111].

Another Ukrainian research is convinced that the meaningful definition of psychological and pedagogical competence remains the subject of discussions among scientists. In scientific and pedagogical literature, it is interpreted as “a set of certain personality qualities, characterized by a high level of professional training for pedagogical activities and effective interaction with subjects of learning, others – as a phenomenon that combines elements of professional and general culture, pedagogical experience, enriched with knowledge, the results of scientific research, multiplied by professionally significant qualities that are manifested in pedagogical activity” [5, 3].

Socio-personal pragmatism and a sense of partnership as a result of the formation and development of the psychological and pedagogical competence of a modern HR manager is significant for his professional self-expression and consists in the awareness of the dependence of the level of social life on the activity of the individual and, conversely, the self-realization of the individual on the state of society. Personality is a source of productive, creative professional activity. In turn, she expects society to create optimal conditions for the realization of her productive and creative potential.

The psychological and pedagogical competence of a modern HR manager is an integral component in the system of professional competence. Psychological and pedagogical competence is a characteristic of a person, which includes such components as understanding of the professional sphere, methodological and psychological spheres of professional activity, the ability to solve psychological and pedagogical, methodological and professional tasks.

Considering the results of previous research, psychological and pedagogical competence of a HR manager can broadly be defined as an integrative feature, which includes knowledge and skills in the field of psychology and pedagogy, necessary for the organization of continuous development as well as wellbeing of the company’s employees, contributes to ensuring the efficiency of professional activity in general and solving complex problems in non-standard situations of the professional environment, as well as inclinations, orientations and strategies for the development of one’s own general and professional personal culture, deepening and accumulation of experience in the field of HR management.

It is clear that educational programs for the initial training of a manager at Bachelor’s, Master’s, and Doctor of Philosophy levels are aimed at forming professional competence and preparing a manager for activity in a professional environment. However, today, because of the rapid spread of knowledge, there is an obvious need for continuing education throughout professional activity. “As companies strive to keep up with the pace of economic changes, new employment opportunities are constantly created requiring professionals with diverse skillsets which might be currently in scarcity. Therefore, corporate L&D organizations need to face this challenge, find effective ways to train employees respectively and thus, enhance the culture of continuous learning in their organizations” [20, 176].

Finding the optimal balance between the organization’s development strategy and the HR management strategy in accordance with the available resources, personnel competence, their ideas, ambitions, initiative is a key factor that determines the competitiveness and effectiveness of the organization’s functioning in a market. HR management at the strategic level allows to simultaneously take into account the goals of the company’s development, the transformation of its external environment in general and the labor market in particular, identify changes in the company’s needs in employees and at the same time adhere to the principle of long-term relations between employees and the company and orientation to their personal development.

Among the practices that have proven their effectiveness in the first decade of the 21st century there is the organization of corporate training. Its specificity lies in the fact that a

company or enterprise organizes the training of employees taking into account the needs, requests, interests of the labour market, the company, and the employee. "Building a culture of continuous learning in any organization is almost impossible without predicting future skills development needs through effective skill assessment" [20, 176].

Personnel development includes continuous training of employees, which in the form of general and professional education gives them the necessary knowledge, skills, and experience; professional development of personnel, the task of which is to improve the professional knowledge and skills of employees; personnel retraining, which means any professional reorientation (the purpose of retraining is to give employees the opportunity to master a new specialty); adaptation of personnel to working conditions; evaluation of candidates offered for a vacant position; business career planning and official and professional promotion of personnel; work with a personnel reserve.

The planning of personnel training begins with the identification of training needs, a process that allows to clearly determine who in the company needs to be trained. The need for training arises at the level of the entire organization or at the level of units and individual employees. Changes in the external environment (economic, legal, technological, etc.), changes within the company (strategy, structure, product) are considered as the sources of the need for personal training. There are two main approaches to identifying training needs: based on employee needs and based on company needs.

Corporate training cannot be effective if it is represented only by single events (business trainings, seminars, courses). Modern corporate training is implemented in the form of a training system aimed at constant assurance of business strategy and tactics of the organization with the necessary intellectual resource. A person, employee is the priority of a modern organization, as well as his knowledge, skills, experience, and relationships. That is why the process of corporate training and personnel development should be constant and continuous. Schuchmann & Seufert claim, that "innovation ability implies requirements in the following two dimensions: individuals are required to learn continuously and reflexive in their daily working processes, the organisation needs to enable and implement innovations through designing frame conditions" [22, 32].

Corporate training is organized with the aim of: systematic knowledge management; search and selection of educational programs and courses; preparation and adaptation of educational programs and courses to the specific needs of the organization; quality control of learning outcomes; formation of personnel reserve; generation of ideas; stimulation of continuous development of the organization; formation of unified corporate values and corporate culture, etc.

Nowadays, businesses try to strengthen their potential by attracting talented, proactive employees and developing the talents of their own employees. "Talent is a primary source of competitive advantage for today's corporate world. The rise in knowledge economy has resulted in more focus on acquiring and retaining talented workforce. The best talent is most critical to achieve best results. An effective talent management system builds the winning organization by proper utilization of strategies framed at different levels" [14, 64].

So, the term "corporate learning" is used here to refer to the company's activity, aimed at organizing continuous training of its employees with the aim of mastering or deepening their knowledge, forming, developing, improving professional and key competencies, revealing their talents, which is organized in accordance with the company's development strategy as a learning organization, taking into account the needs and interests of the staff.

Conclusion

The purpose of the current study was to determine the main concepts and categories of the research devoted to the study of HR managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation in the framework of corporate training.

This study has identified that competence is a basic characteristic that determines the ability and readiness of an individual to solve problems and tasks in daily life, based on the practical use of the knowledge system, as well as life experience.

The most obvious finding to emerge from this study is that professional competence is an integral characteristic of a manager which encompasses the system of knowledge, skills for its practical application, personal and professional values and attitudes, which allow him to solve problems in professional environment which is characterised with rapidity of change and uncertainty.

One of the more significant findings to emerge from this study is that psychological and pedagogical competence of a HR manager is an integrative feature, which includes knowledge and skills in the field of psychology and pedagogy, necessary for the organization of continuous development as well as wellbeing of the company's employees, contributes to ensuring the efficiency of professional activity in general and solving complex problems in non-standard situations of the professional environment, as well as inclinations, orientations and strategies for the development of one's own general and professional personal culture, deepening and accumulation of experience in the field of HR management.

This study has found that generally corporate training should be interpreted as following: the company's activity, aimed at organizing continuous training of its employees with the aim of mastering or deepening their knowledge, forming, developing, improving g professional and key competencies, revealing their talents, which is organized in accordance with the company's development strategy as a learning organization, taking into account the needs and interests of the staff.

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